

Adaptation of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy for Couples Therapy

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between couples is complicated and composed of many various intertwined phenomena. People generally choose persons who have similar childhood experiences as themselves. Their positive and negative unfulfilled needs align together, and they attract each other. Because of the similar traumas they may be triggered easily and find themselves in an impasse. (Bal, 2020) Couples may have difficulty resolving these complex problems by themselves and they may need to address a specialist who is an objective authority. Various kinds of psychotherapy techniques may be used for the couples. Sometimes an eclectic style that is a combination of some of the psychotherapy methods may be used to resolve the problems of the couples who have conflicts. There may be many reasons for these conflicts; however, the main reasons are the rules of the relationship and who will define these rules.

ACT (Acceptance and Commitment Therapy) is a very reasonable psychotherapy method that may be used for couples therapy for it has so many convenient features.

At the essence of this psychotherapy method there are keeping in touch with the moment, accepting the feelings and thoughts, dissociating from them, notice the context, values and actions.

Abstract

People unite and establish a relationship and family union. They integrate and proliferate. Cohabitation (living together) may sometimes be hard, especially after World War II, when some social, economic and cultural changes have taken place, couples began expecting more from a relationship. The connection

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Introduction

There are some qualifications for a healthy relationship between couples. First, they provide their necessities to maintain their lives. They have effective communication among them and have the skills to cope with the problems. They share their feelings sincerely and clearly with each other. They are empathetic and sensitive about each other's feelings and concerns. They accept each other's individual differences and respect those differences. They transmit their love, affection and interest for each other. They have a common sense of humor, and they make jokes and laugh together. They have the capacity to cooperate and take responsibility. They express their admiration for each other. They enjoy sharing some of their spare time together. Their spiritual and religious values are compatible.

Methodology

All these conditions sometimes may not be easy to realize. Couples may have some problems; they may find themselves in trouble and may not be able to resolve their own problems. In these conditions they intervene in therapies. Couples therapy has been addressed since the 1950's. There are various kinds of psychotherapy models that have been applied according to the problems of the couples. BDT, Solution-focused therapy, Gestalt, Gottman, Imago relationship therapy, Schema therapy, Rational- emotional therapy, Sexual therapy, Metacognitive therapy and Acceptance and commitment therapy are some of them. Therapist decides what kind of therapy is more convenient for the couple according to the couple's problems. Acceptance and commitment therapy approach for couples therapy is very

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compatible in so many ways for couples therapy if one member of the couples has not any serious disorder such as bipolar and schizophrenia. For a successful therapy, empathetic understanding, unconditional acceptance and positive and non-judgmental point of view are needed. This is the therapeutic relation itself. (Keçe, 2018).

Couples Therapy

People decide to get together, make their relationship legal and establish a family union. While they maintain their lives together, they have certain rules they must agree and obey. In order this relationship lasts and becomes a happy one, they should compromise on the rules and evade from stress and anxiety. If one member of the couple feels frustrated, obstructed or abused, a conflict begins among the couple. Marriage is a complex and complicated relationship that contains various layers in flow of life. If the balance is disrupted and problems emerge, 'Couples Therapy' may resolve the problem.

Generally, these conflicts among the couples are about, which rules they are going to obey, the rules that may contradict with each other and about who will determine the rules. 'You and me' struggles, threatening, physical or verbal attacks cause despair. There may be distinct reasons for these conflicts: The lack of communication, unfulfilled emotional needs, sexual dissatisfaction, betrayal, disputes about managing money issues, problems about the families of the couples, authority problems about children and differences between political and religious beliefs.

When a member of the couple or both the members of the couple notices a need for support, they apply for couple's therapy.

The approach of couples therapy emerged in the years of 1950's. Rapid social and technological change after World War II, caused some psychological and social change as well. It affected the attitude and expectations of the individuals on a large scale. People began

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expecting a much higher level of standard about happiness. As a result of these improvements, relationship problems and conflicts have increased among couples, so; the necessity of couples therapy has become widespread. (Özgüven, 2014).

The goal of couples therapy is to resolve the problems and conflicts among couples. During the therapy, the attitudes of the couples, their struggling process, their forcing, complying, compromising, cooperating and evading attitudes are being dwelled on. The reasons for the problems and the way of accusing each other are as well emphasized. The therapist tries to find the solution to resolve the problems with a different method than the couple have used before. He tries to teach them solution oriented new options of skills and attitudes.

Literature Review

Interactions they couldn't have built among themselves may easily have been established by the help of a therapist. Some therapists may decide to confer one by one with the couple, some of them may prefer to consult them together according to the problem or situation. In some situations, it is provided that one of the couple of members intervenes by another therapist.

A specialist that signifies authority may help them to cooperate easily. The probability of their achieving interaction is much higher when they come together under the supervision of an objective guide.

There may be some problems that the therapist may face during the therapies:

Partners may insistently defend each other and block to encounter the real problem. 2. One partner defining the other as 'ill' and problematic, one of the partners being under psychiatric treatment, 3. One of the partners may have some other physical illness. 4. One of the partner's not volunteering to attend the therapy. (Özgüven, 2014)

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Therapy always begins with a contract. Who will come to the session and when depends upon the flow of the therapy. Financial regulations are made. The adversity that the couple experiences and the strengths are detected. The sources of the adversity, the frequency of the hardship that is experienced and the intensity of the hardship are taken into consideration. The area that the change has been expected to realize is defined.

To evaluate the problems of the couples there are some scales that measure marital satisfaction, binary harmony, positive and negative situations, changing areas and conflicting and disagreement areas of the couples. The attitudes may be scaled from rigid to flexible. Balanced and functional areas are measured. Integrity is scaled from irrelevant-uncommunicative to too intertwined. The capacity to face the challenges, being in harmony, and effective communication are the powerful sides of a couple. (Lebow, 2019)

To terminate the therapies depends upon the length of the treatment however the client is the first person who decides to end the therapies. When the clients reach their aim, the therapy is evaluated as successful. The process of the therapy must be revised and

focused on if all the targets are reached, which ones couldn't have been achieved and which factors have contributed to the change. At the end of the therapy for the earnings to endure, some special efforts may be required, and these must be defined.

Couples Therapy applications may be in various forms, or it may be in an eclectic form. If a member of the couple doesn't have any serious psychological disorder such as bipolar and schizophrenia, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy is proper and so convenient to adopt for Couples Therapy.

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy Emphasizes acceptance as a way of coping with negative feelings, thoughts, symptoms and conditions. It supports you with your values and goals by helping you to bind with constructive activities. (<https://basarihastanesi.com/makale/kabul-ve-kararlilik-terapisi-act-terapi-nedir/>)

Acceptance and Commitment Theory has some functions. The first function is the context, and it is the main function that dissociates this therapy from the other BDT therapies. Context is best understood with the metaphor of a plastic bottle. Suppose that you're sitting on a bank in a park. Someone came near you and extended a plastic bottle towards your mouth. This sudden movement irritates you and makes you move back. However, if you are a runner, run 10 kilometers and reach the finish point in a tired to death position and someone gives you the same bottle, you get it, drink it and feel thankful. Function depends upon the context. If the context of the situation changes, the function changes as well. To understand the function and the context of the attitudes supports the basis of the intervention. (Bennet and Oliver, 2023)

ACT (Acceptance and Commitment Therapy) directs the client to pay attention to questions such as where the client is trying to reach with this attitude or from where he is trying to move away.

Findings

The first function is to be in touch with the moment. The goal of the therapist is to increase resilience and make the client realize with which ideas, thoughts, images and memories does the client unite and from which of them does he evade. Which ideas, thoughts, images and memories carry the client to the past and which of them carry him to the future. Which of the thoughts about himself does he unite and what is it that he wants to achieve in the future. What

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are the most important things in his life? What are his aims and are his aims consistent with his values? (Köroğlu, 2017).

The second function of the therapy is acceptance of all the feelings, thoughts and situations. This function supports the client with noticing his own inner processes.

even if they are negative or unwanted. This process doesn't mean to be in a passive position. Contrary, it is an active and flexible process. It is not enduring, bearing or tolerating. It is the noticing and acceptance of the feelings and thoughts without trying to intervene, without trying to obstruct or decrease them. They are the reality. The client should not deny, and he must realize the reality. The metaphor of 'sky' is used to explain the acceptance function of the therapy: A person should feel like a 'sky' when the subject is his thoughts and feelings. He should realize his own real thoughts and feelings. He should be sure that they will come and go and change in a while if he doesn't hold on to them. They are like the 'weather conditions. Today is cloudy, tomorrow may be sunny. He should see the real weather and live accordingly.

The third function is 'dissociation'. The same metaphor may be used here as well. Dissociation is separating from the feelings and thoughts. They will come and go, but they are not you. To dissociate the client from his thoughts and feelings, the therapist uses metaphors. There are some common metaphors that have been often used by therapists through therapy. 'The passengers in the bus' metaphor (Köroğlu, 2017, p 255) describes the client as the bus driver and the passengers as his thoughts and feelings. Sometimes during the drive, these passengers tell you what to do in a threatening way. They disturb you all the time if you don't do what they tell you, sometimes you do what they want from you however then you are not on your own way anymore. They direct you. To convince them or to kick them out of the bus are some ways of coping with them; however, in both ways you get tired, and you lose time. As you try to control your thoughts and feelings you lose more control. With this metaphor, the therapist makes the client realize his thoughts and feelings and dissociate from them.

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Another metaphor that is used frequently is ‘pulling rope with the monster’. Here the monster signifies your powerful thoughts and emotions, and the rope signifies the struggle among you and them. The monster is much stronger than you and what you do is a useless and inconclusive effort.

Argument

Another metaphor is ‘the man in the draw well’. You are in the well and trying to get out of it. You notice a shovel nearby excitedly you decide to use it. However, as you do it, you find yourself in deeper depths. It looks like the ‘leaving the rope’ analogy’. You don’t need that thought, it is useless, you cannot get to where you want to reach by thinking this way. By using these metaphors, the therapist aims to show the client how he is stuck to useless ways of thinking. (Köroğlu, 2017)

The fourth function is the sense of self. Conceptualized self is all about you, all the thoughts, beliefs, ideas, images, judgements and memories that define you. However, if anyone holds on to this self-more than necessary, he can’t be flexible and cannot cope with the hardship of life. ‘Self-as awareness’ is more in touch with the moment and this level of self can be more resilient. He can observe, perceive and evaluate the processes without judging.

Values are the fifth function of the therapy. Values are the basic principles that guide and motivate us throughout life. These are especially important for every individual. When anyone is in a psychological conflict, he may easily disregard these values and he finds himself quite far away from his focus. Values are like compasses that show us the way and keep us on the right path. To define and concretize values and the goals, the therapists use ‘the two children in the car’ metaphor. There are two children in the car with their mother driving, one of them is enjoying the drive, looking out of the window, singing, enjoying, the second one is asking

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all the time ‘aren’t we there yet?’ The first one has values of his own, the second one is focused on the goal strictly and cannot become aware of any other possibilities in life.

Paul Flaxman developed an exercise to guide the couples through diagnose and differentiate among their values and goals. This exercise is called ‘Flaxman Maneuver’ (Bennet, 2023, p.154). The therapist wants the couples to write their personal values in one paper and write useless thoughts in another paper. During this exercise couples see how they are detained from their goals because of their useless thoughts.

Actions are the sixth function of the therapy. They substantially cause the clients to address therapy. When anyone perceives that he cannot take a step and start a

value-focused activity, he realizes that he needs support. The six dimensions and functions of ACT constitutes a hexagonal model, and it is mentioned as ‘Hexaflex’ in Psychology. With all the precious functions that ACT includes, it becomes an unbelievably valuable and useful tool to support the couples in perceiving their own cognition and give them new opportunities to settle their problems and to compromise with their partners. A Very Short Dialog of Adaptation of ACT to Couples Therapy

Therapist: Welcome Arzu and Mehmet how are you?

Arzu: Fine thanks

Mehmet: Thank you so much.

T: Can you please tell me how I can help you?

A: We have problems with my husband. We have been married for thirty years however recently he has changed a lot.

T: In what ways?

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A: He wants to have more time for himself and pass more time out without me. He thinks I'm blocking him and sometimes treats me rudely.

M: I'm 58 years old, have worked so much in life and now just retired. Maybe I'm in andropause.

T: Let's stop and stay calm for a moment. Try to get in touch with the moment. Notice your feelings.

M: I want to enjoy life before I get so old, before it's too late I wish to live my life.

A: I cannot cope with my feelings and feel I'm not loved anymore.

T: Let's conceptualize your situation. You both are enduring a period.

Anthropause is a hard period. If it couldn't have been the problem, you wouldn't have this kind of problem. To realize the contextual situation: Suppose that somebody holds a bottle of water towards your mouth suddenly when you're sitting at a bank in the park. Would you be irritated? Now suppose that you have run 10 km and reached the finish line, and somebody is giving a bottle towards your mouth. What would you do? They're different, aren't they? This is the contextual difference.

T: Now let's see, I understand both of you. Mehmet, is this an effortless way of enjoying life if you offend your wife? Is this all you expect from life? What would you do if you were completely free? How would you treat others and yourself? What would you let go?

M: I only want to have free time then come home. I love my wife and am content with my marriage. I wasn't aware that I offended my wife.

T. Thank you Mehmet, okay Arzu where do you see yourself in life in ten years?

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A: I feel comfortable in my marriage, I love my husband. In future I wish to get old with him. I wish to go on writing books.

M: She tenses me and makes me feel guilty when I go out by myself.

A: No, I don't, I only want to spend more time with him. When he goes, I feel that he doesn't love me anymore and I worry that our marriage will deteriorate, and I have concerns that I may lose him.

T: Think that you're pulling a rope, you and a monster, you are trying to win because you want to get rid of falling into a well. Who will win, you or the monster?

M: The monster

A: Yes, of course

T: Now, you're pulling and making a useless effort. If you leave the rope no one will fall into the well. Try to dissociate from the feelings that won't carry you happily to the future. Try to empathize with your partner.

A: Thank you so much

M: Thanks a lot.

Discussion and Conclusion

Family life and relationships are not stable, they are versatile and changeable. This is called the family life cycle. Couples face various situations during their different time spans. Developmental processes may comprise various patterns that cause conflict. Flirting period, raising children, menopause and andropause periods may create new conflicts and decrease

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satisfaction of the couples. Several other problems, including the economic and social ones may arise. Somewhere along the way couples may need professional help.

Couples Therapy indicates the application of science and ethics to family life. This way it comprises cognizance that comes from various areas such as social psychology, individual psychology, philosophy, philosophy of science, semantics, sociology and anthropology. For the therapist to construct an effective therapy for his clients, he must correlate all the knowledge that comes from these areas with the perspective and culture of the family dynamics and build a bridge among them. (Lebow, 2019)

ACT is a therapy model very compatible with couple's therapy. It supports couples at the point of discovering what is important and meaningful for the couples as a couple and individually as well. It also helps couples which steps should be taken and how to achieve a meaningful life. It guides couples through the process of therapeutic.

healing by providing them to decrease the effect of their feelings and thoughts. It also teaches them how to get out of the automatic pilot skillfully.

ACT has some functions that step by step with these functions, the therapist supports the couples and helps them resolve their problems. Therapists that use ACT especially apply the 'Hexaflex' model through the therapies. After he perceives the details of the problems of the couple, if he believes that ACT is compatible for the couple, he begins applying ACT 's six components model. First step is trying to support the client through providing him to be now and get in touch with the very moment he lives in, to get out of the automatic pilot and pay attention to the moment. Then he provides his client to accept and not judge all the feelings, thoughts and situations. However, he wants him to learn how to dissociate from his own feelings and thoughts. He uses the power of various kinds of metaphors during this process. He also tries to make his client be aware of his conceptual self. At the end he guides his client towards his goals accompanied by his values through the therapy. ACT is very compatible with

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the couples therapy if one of the members doesn't have any serious diagnoses such as bipolar or schizophrenia.

Limitations

This research is limited to the extent of the data in the world literature. The research is restricted to the research about the related subjects. It is limited to literature surveys.

Notices

Assessment: This study was assessed by internal and external advisors.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declared no conflicts of interest in relation to this article. ("Research on the Reform and Innovation of Preschool Education ... - Hindawi")

Financial Support: The author declared no financial support for the investigation of this research.

Ethical Declaration

This study aims to ensure that scientific research is made in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, respect for the findings and creations of others and aims to realize these principles in the field of related disciplines.

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